

MICROBIAL REMEDIATION OF HEAVY METALS CONTAMINATION IN SOIL

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- **OUTLINE**
- **INTRODUCTION**
- **DEFINITION OF TERMS**
- **MICROORGANISMS INVOLVED IN HEAVY METAL REMEDIATION**
- **SOURCES OF HEAVY METALS IN THE SOIL**
- **EFFECT OF HEAVY METALS IN THE SOIL, PLANT, ANIMALS AND MAN**
- **MECHANISMS OF MICROBIAL REMEDIATION**
- **RELEVANCE OF MICROBIAL REMEDIATION**
- **CONCLUSION**
- **RECOMMENDATION**
- **REFERENCES.**

Abstract: Heavy metals are metals with density above 5g/cm^3 which occur naturally in the environment. However, the indiscriminate discharge arising from geochemical and anthropogenic activities have remained a galloping source of contamination in the ecosystem. They can be mitigated through the use of microorganisms such as *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus* and *Aspergillus* species. The mechanisms utilized by microbes in heavy metals remediation include change in biochemical pathways that obstruct metal uptake, enzymatic transformation of metals to harmless forms and the use of exact effluent system for reducing intracellular concentration of metals. Factors such as physicochemical and biological are known to influence heavy metal remediation in contaminated sites. Prolonged exposure of such heavy metals could have deleterious health effects on human life including inhibition of libido in male reproductive systems and obstruction of ovulation in females as well as in other terrestrial and aquatic biota. The use of microorganisms in cleaning up heavy metals contaminated sites is a viable and sustainable one as it overcomes the drawbacks encountered in other methods of heavy metal treatments. This leads to a healthy environment and guarantees public health of it teeming citizens.

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Continuously, increasing the population in world with the growth of industry, there has been a considerable increase in the discharge of industrial Waste to the soil and aquatic environment, chiefly soil and water, which has led to the accumulation of heavy metals, especially in urban areas. Slow in a row down of heavy metals also takes place through leaching, plant uptake, erosion and deflation.

The unsystematic release of heavy metals into the soil and waters is a major health hazard concern worldwide, as they cannot be broken down to non-toxic forms and therefore have long-lasting effects on the ecosystem. Many of them are toxic even at very low concentrations; arsenic, cadmium, chromium, copper; lead, mercury, nickel, selenium, silver, zinc etc. Are not only cyto toxic but also carcinogenic and mutagenic in nature.

Plants in very small amounts or their growth and optimum performance require some metals. However, the increasing concentration of several metals in soil and waters due to industrial revolution has created an alarming situation for human life, aquatic biota and soil biota.

In order to make the environment healthier for human beings ,contaminated water bodies and land need to be rectified to make them free from heavy metals and trace elements.

There are several techniques to remove these heavy metals, including chemical precipitation, oxidation or reduction, filtration, ion exchange, reverse osmosis, membrane technology, evaporation and electrochemical treatment. However, most of these techniques become ineffective when the concentrations of heavy metals are less than 100 mg/L. Most heavy metal salts are water-soluble and get dissolved in wastewater, which means they cannot be separated by physical separation methods. Additionally, physico-chemical methods are ineffective or expensive when the concentration of heavy metals is very low.

Alternately, biological methods like biosorption and/or bioaccumulation for removal of heavy metals may be an attractive alternative to physico-chemical methods. Use of microorganisms and plants for remediation purposes is thus a possible solution for heavy metal pollution because it includes sustainable remediation technologies to rectify and re-establish the natural condition of soil.

However, introduction of heavy metals into the soil causes considerable modification of the microbial community, despite their vital importance for the growth of microorganisms at relatively low concentrations. The modification of the microbial make up is mainly brought about by exerting an inhibitory action through blockage of essential functional groups, displacement of essential metal ions or modification of active conformations of biological molecules. The response of microbial communities to heavy metals depends on the concentration and availability of heavy metals and is a complex process, which are controlled by multiple factors, such as type of metal, the nature of the medium and microbial species.

1.1. DEFINITION OF TERMS

➤ MICROBIAL:

A unicellular or small multicellular organism including bacteria, protozoa, some algae, fungi, viruses, and some worms, especially that are injurious to other organisms

➤ HEAVY METALS

Heavy metals are defined as metallic elements that have a relatively high density compared to water. With the assumption that heaviness and toxicity are inter-related, heavy metals also include metalloids, such as arsenic, that are able to induce toxicity at low level of exposure.

➤ BIOREMEDIATION

Bioremediation is a process used to treat contaminated media, including water, soil and subsurface material, by altering environmental conditions to stimulate growth of microorganisms and degrade the target pollutants. Bioremediation is a general concept that includes all those processes and actions that take place in order to biotransform an environment, already altered by contaminants, to its original status.

Bioremediation uses primarily microorganisms or microbial processes to degrade and transform environmental contaminants into harmless or less toxic forms.

➤ SOIL

Soil is a mixture of organic matter, minerals, gases, liquids, and organisms that together support life.

The soil is a very essential component for all the living organisms. Especially for plants, it's considered as the basic living factor. Soil serves as a nutrient media for the growth of plants. The soil is not essential for agriculture production but also toward maintained all life form.

These life-supporting functions include, for example, recycling of carbon and essential nutrients of all living materials, filtering, and storage of water, regulation of the atmosphere and biological control of pests.

➤ HEAVY METALS

Heavy metals are natural elements in the environment. However anthropogenic releases, including industrial and domestic effluents, urban storm, water runoff, landfill leachate, atmospheric sources, and dumping of sewage sludge can give rise to higher concentrations of the metals relative to the normal background values. The term "heavy metal" refers to a metal or metalloid with a density exceeding 5g/cm^3 and is usually associated with pollution and toxicity, although some of these elements (essential metals) are actually required by organisms at low concentrations (Adriano, 2001). Several heavy metals, such as copper, zinc, and iron, are essential for the physiological functioning of living organisms, but they all become toxic at high concentrations. The toxicity of a metal depends on the metal itself, its total concentration, the availability of the metal to the organism, and the organism itself.

Depending on the organism and the metal, different modes of action are recognized: binding to macromolecules (proteins, DNA, RNA), disruption of enzymatic functions, catalysis of radical formation, etc. For example, zinc (Zn) is a component found in a variety

of enzymes (dehydrogenases, proteinases, peptidases), but it is also involved in the metabolism of carbohydrates, proteins, phosphate, auxins, and in

RNA and ribosome formation in plants (Kabata-pendias et al., 2001, Mangel and Kirkby, 1982).

Heavy metal appears to include all metals of the periodic table with atomic numbers greater than 20, generally excluding the alkali metal and the alkali earth. Heavy metals are metallic, naturally occurring compounds that have a very high density greater than 5g/cm³; compared to other metals at least five times the density of water. They are one of the most persistent pollutants in soil and water.

Heavy metals can be divided into two categories: **Essential and Non-Essential** on the basis of their role in living systems.

1. Essential heavy metals such as Mn, Fe, Ni, Zn are needed by living organisms for their growth, development and physiological functions, while
2. Non-essential heavy metals such as Cd, Pb, Hg and As are not needed by living organisms for any physiological function (Gohre et al., 2006).

Abundant amounts of heavy metals present in soils cause the reduction in quality and quantity of food preventing plants growth, uptake of nutrients, metabolic and physiological processes. Heavy metals are toxic to humans. Even small doses can have serious consequences. Severe effects on animals may include reduced growth and development, cancer, organ damage, nervous system damage, and in extreme cases, death. To help mitigate the negative impacts of heavy metals on the health of humans, animals, and the environment, a variety of remediation processes exists.

However, anthropogenic activities such as mining have resulted in elevated levels of these contaminants in the environment. By definition, any toxic metal may be called a heavy metal, irrespective of its atomic mass or density. The classification includes some metalloids, transition metals, basic metals, lanthanides and actinides and metals of groups III to V of the periodic table. Examples include As, Pb, Hg, Cd, Cr, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Se, Al, Cs, Mn, Mo, Sr, U, Be and Bi (Cairney et al., 1993).

Industrial pollution generally increases the heavy metal content of the soil. The environmental risk due to soil pollution especially heavy metals is importance for agricultural and non-agricultural areas. Because heavy metals, which are potentially harmful to plants, soil microorganisms and human health persist in soil or a very long time. When the heavy metals present in the natural condition do not act as toxic up to certain extent. When the concentration reaches the maximum level or up to the final permissible level heavy metals will be converted in to toxic in nature and it will lead to the dangerous effects on the surrounding system (Ahirwar et al., 2018).

Some metals are essential to life and play irreplaceable roles as sources of vitamins, and minerals in the functioning of body organs. All living organisms require varying amounts of metals but become toxic at higher concentrations (NRC, 1993). Other metals have no useful role in the human physiology. Examples of such elements are arsenic, lead, and mercury. They may be toxic even at low levels of exposure. Once absorbed by the body, heavy metals

continue to accumulate in vital organs like the brain, liver, bones, and kidneys, for years or decades causing serious health consequences (Norris et al., 1993).

2.1 MICROORGANISMS INVOLVED IN HEAVY METALS

Bioremediation is the most effective management tool to manage the polluted environment and recover contaminated soil. The process of bioremediation uses various agents such as bacteria, fungi, algae and higher plants as major tools in treating heavy metals present in the environment.

Microbes are very helpful to remediate the contaminated environment. Environmental pollution is a very big problem because of hazardous waste that led to scarcity of clean water and disturbances of soil thus limiting crop production. Bioremediation uses biological agents, mainly microorganisms i.e., bacteria, fungi and yeast to clean up contaminated water. In bioremediation processes, microorganism use the contaminants as nutrient or energy sources. Bioremediation process involves biotransformation and biodegradation by transforming contaminants to non –hazardous or less hazardous chemicals.

Organism groups and soil processes that should be considered in hazard and risk assessment of soil contamination (according to Eijsackers and Lokke, 1992)

1. Taxonomic groups: **Microorganisms:** *Saprotrophic fungi, mycorrhizal fungi, bacteria*

Invertebrates: *Protozoa, Nematoda, Oligochaeta (earthworms, enchytraeids), microarthropods (Collembola, Acarina etc.), macroinvertebrates (Isopoda, Diplopoda etc.), insects and their larvae in soils*

Higher plants

2. Functional groups:
Primary producers
Decomposers
Herbivores Predators and parasites

2. Soil processes:
Decomposition, soil respiration
Nutrient mineralization, nitrification
other enzyme activities

Soil animals as a risk food web transfer of the contaminants In some cases soil animals may transfer contaminants accumulated in them to the above-ground food webs. Especially the earthworms, having considerable ability to accumulate contaminants from soil into their

bodies, and having relatively low sensitivity to many of these compounds, can be an important transfer route from soil to the above ground ecosystems (Eijsackers, 1998). Many vertebrate animals, like badgers, foxes and several bird species, are frequently feeding on earthworms. Because bioconcentration factors (concentration in earthworms vs. that in soil) have been observed to be quite high, for e.g. heavy metals are often exceeded, even in normal agricultural soils (Spurgeon and Hopkin, 1996).

Recently, biological remediation process have also been devised to either precipitate effectively immobilize inorganic pollutants such as heavy metals.

Stimulation of microorganisms is achieved by the addition of growth substances, nutrients, terminal electron acceptor or donors or some combination thereby resulting in an increase in organic pollutant degradation and bio-transformation. The energy and carbon are obtained through the metabolism of organic compounds by the microbes involved in bioremediation processes. Often, the microorganisms metabolize the chemicals to produce carbon dioxide or methane, water and biomass

Biodegradation is the breaking down of organic or bioaccumulation and biotransformation of inorganic compounds into environmental friendly compounds. Bioremediation may employed in order to attack specific contaminants, such as chlorinated pesticides that are degraded by bacteria, or a more general approach may be taken, such as oil spills that are broken down using multiple techniques including the addition of fertilizer to facilitate the decomposition of crude oil by bacteria. Not all contaminants are readily treated through the use of bioremediation; heavy metals such as cadmium, lead are not readily absorbed or captured by microorganism.

2.2 Principle of Bioremediation.

There are three essential components needed for bioremediation. These three components are **microorganisms, food, and nutrients**. These three main components are known as the bioremediation triangle. Microorganisms are found almost everywhere on earth with the exception of active volcanoes. Microorganisms find the food they eat in the soil or water where they live. However, if a contaminant is present it can become an additional food source for the microorganisms. The contaminant serves two useful purposes for the microbes. First, the contaminant provides a source of carbon needed for growth. Second, the microbes obtain energy by breaking chemical bonds and transferring electrons away from the contaminant. This is known as an oxidation-reduction reaction. The contaminant that loses electrons is oxidized and the chemical that gains the electrons (electron acceptor) is reduced. The energy gained from the electron transfer is used along with the carbon and some electrons to produce more cells.

Microbes generally use oxygen as an electron acceptor but nitrate, sulfate, iron, and CO₂ are also commonly used.

Most bioremediation systems are run under aerobic conditions, but running a system under anaerobic condition may permit microbial organisms to degrade otherwise recalcitrant molecules.

2.3 Role of biotechnology in bioremediation

Biotechnology utilizes the application of genetic engineering to improve the efficiency and cost, which are factors in the future widespread exploitation of microorganisms to reduce the environmental burden of toxic substances. The need of the most efficient environmental biotechnological process technique called bioremediation, in which is an emerging approach to rehabilitating areas contaminated by pollutants. Biological agents have proved their capacity for remediation, however, their long term and large scale use needs the application of genetic tools. Genetically modified microorganisms have the potential for bioremediation applications in groundwater, soil and activated sludge environments, exhibiting enhanced degradative capabilities encompassing a wide range of chemical contaminants. There are several examples where the use of biotechnology has increased the natural capacity of biological forms. *Bacillus thuringensis* has been used for the removal of oil spills. *Deinococcus radiodurans* (radioactive resistant bacteria) has been modified to consume and digest toluene and ionic mercury from highly radioactive waste..

Microorganisms that carry out biodegradation in different environments are identified as active members of microbial consortiums. These microorganisms include: *Xanthofacter*, *Penicillium*, *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Flavobacterium*, *Mycrobacterium*, *Nitrosomonas etc* . There are some groups of microbes which are being used in bioremediation such as;

2.4 Aerobic:

Aerobic bacteria recognized for their degradative abilities are *Pseudomonas*, *Sphingomonas*, *Rhodococcus* and *Mycobacterium*. These microbes are to degrade pesticides and hydrocarbons, both alkanes and polyaromatic compounds. Many of these bacteria use the contaminant as the sole source of carbon and energy.

2.5 Anaerobic:

Anaerobic bacteria are not as frequently used as aerobic bacteria. There is an increasing interest in aerobic bacteria used for bioremediation of polychlorinated biphenyls in river sediments, dechlorination of the solvent trichloroethylene and chloroform. The goal in bioremediation is to stimulate microorganisms with nutrients and the other chemicals that will enable them to destroy the contamination. Microbes could be isolated from almost all types of environmental conditions and also had a wide range of adaptability. It can survive from zero to extremely high and desert conditions. In water, it can survive in presence and absence of oxygen and also in presence of hazardous compounds or waste stream. Bacteria, fungi, yeast and algae can remove heavy metals and radionuclide from aqueous solution in substantial quantities.

MECHANISMS

To survive under metal stressed condition, bacteria have evolved several types of mechanisms.

These mechanisms of removal of heavy metals include the efflux of metal ions outside the cell, accumulation and forms complex of the metal ions inside the cell and later reduce the toxic metal ions to a non-toxic state. The microorganisms involved in this process may belong to bacteria, fungi, yeast and algae. Potent metal biosorbents under the class of bacteria include the genera of *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Streptomyces* and *P. aeruginosa*. Amongst the various microorganisms, fungal biomasses were very effective due to presence of high

percentage of cell wall material, which may have the excellent metal binding capacity. Many fungi and yeast have excellent biosorption potential includes the genera of *Rhizopus*, *Aspergillus*, *Streptovercillum* and *Sacchromyces*. High levels of heavy metals are harmful to biota in environment including microorganisms. For endurance under metal-stressed environment, plant growth promoting Rhizobacteria have evolved several mechanisms by which they can immobilize, mobilize or transform metals rendering them inactive to tolerate the uptake of heavy metal ions.

2.1. Sources of Heavy Metal in the Environment

Heavy metals occur naturally in the environment from pedogenetic processes of weathering of parent materials and also through anthropogenic sources. The most significant natural sources are weathering of minerals, erosion and volcanic activity, while the anthropogenic sources depend upon human activities such as mining, smelting, electroplating, use of pesticides and phosphate fertilizer discharge, as well biosolids (e.g., livestock manures, composts, and municipal sewage sludge), atmospheric deposition, etc. The disturbance of nature's slowly occurring geochemical cycle of metals by man results in accumulation of one or more of heavy metals in the soil and waters, and above defined levels, this is enough to cause risk to human health, plants, animals and aquatic biota. The heavy metals essentially become contaminants in the soil and water environment because of their excess generation by natural.

Industrial pollution generally increases the heavy metal content of the soil. The environmental risk due to soil pollution especially heavy metals is importance for agricultural and non-agricultural areas. Because heavy metals, which are potentially harmful to plants, soil microorganisms and human health persist in soils for a very long time. When the heavy metals present in the natural condition do not act as toxic up to certain extent. When the concentration reaches the maximum level or up to the final permissible level heavy metals will be converted in to toxic in nature and it will lead to the dangerous effects on the surrounding system (Ahirwar et al., 2018). Some metals are essential to life and play irreplaceable roles as sources of vitamins, and minerals in the functioning of body organs. All living organisms require varying amounts of metals but become toxic at higher concentrations (NRC, 1993). Other metals have no useful role in the human physiology. Examples of such elements are arsenic, lead, and mercury. They may be toxic even at low levels of exposure. Once absorbed by the body, heavy metals continue to accumulate in vital organs like the brain, liver, bones, and kidneys, for years or decades causing serious health consequences (Norris et al., 1993).

2.2. Sources and Effect of Heavy Metal in Soil: Its Bioremediation

These remediation processes are broadly **classified into chemical and biological**. Biological remediation processes (microbial remediation and phytoremediation) are indicated to be very effective in the treatment of heavy metal pollutants in soil and wastewater. **Microbial remediation** is the restoration of the environment and its quality using microorganisms, such as bacteria, fungi, protozoan, and algae. The use of plants to degrade or accumulate toxic metals, thereby leading to a reduction in the bioavailability of the contaminant in the soil or water.

A better approach than these traditional methods is to completely destroy the pollutants if possible, or at least to transform them into innocuous substances. Some technologies that have been used are high-temperature incineration and various types of chemical decomposition (e.g., base-catalyzed dechlorination, UV oxidation).

Bioremediation is a natural process which relies on bacteria, fungi, and plants to alter contaminants as these organisms carry out their normal life functions. Metabolic processes of these organisms are capable of using chemical contaminants as an energy source, rendering the contaminants harmless or less toxic products in most cases. Thus, bioremediation provides an alternative tool to destroy or render the harmful contaminants through biological activity and this method is also cost-effective (Kamaluddin et al., 2003).

Bioremediation/ Phytoremediation and Rhizoremediation, Microflora associated with plants; endophytic bacteria, rhizosphere bacteria, and mycorrhizae have the potential to degrade heavy metals in association with plants and this process is termed rhizoremediation. Thus bioremediation, phytoremediation, and rhizoremediation contribute significantly to the fate of hazardous waste (heavy metals) and can be used to remove these unwanted compounds from the biosphere.

Bioremediation processes can also be assessed through a multifaceted approach such as Natural attenuation, sensing environmental pollution, metabolic pathway engineering, applying phyto and microbial diversity to problematic sites, plant-endophyte partnerships and systems biology (Asha et al., 2013). Enhancement of these polluted soil residues with different organic amendments like manure compost, biosolids, MSW will lead to increased bioavailability which in turn will act as nutrients for microorganisms and also a conditioner to improve the physical properties and fertility of the soils (Jin et al., 2011).

Phytoremediation, a fast emerging technology is an eco-friendly, low tech, cost-effective, green alternative to the problem (Meagher et al., 2000).

Table 1:	Effect of heavy metal toxicity on plants.	Reference
Heavy metal	Plant	Toxic effect on plant
As	Rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i>)	Reduction in seed germination; decrease in seedling height; reduced leaf area and dry matter production
		[35, 36]

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum*) Reduced fruit yield; decrease in

leaf fresh weight [37]

Canola (*Brassica napus*) Stunted growth; chlorosis; wilting [38]

Cd

Wheat (*Triticum* sp.) Reduction in seed germination; decrease

in plant nutrient content; reduced

shoot and root length [33, 39]

Garlic (*Allium sativum*) Reduced shoot growth;

Cd accumulation [40]

Maize (*Zea mays*)

Reduced shoot growth;

inhibition of root growth [41]

Co

Tomato

(*Lycopersicon esculentum*)

Reduction in plant

nutrient content

[42]

Mung

bean (*Vigna radiata*)

Reduction in antioxidant

enzyme activities; decrease in

plant sugar, starch, amino acids,

and protein content

[43]

Radish

(*Raphanus sativus*)

Reduction in shoot length, root length,

and total leaf area; decrease in chlorophyll

content; reduction in plant nutrient content

and antioxidant enzyme activity; decrease

in plant sugar, amino acid, and protein

content

[44]

Cr
Wheat (*Triticum* sp.) Reduced shoot and root growth [45, 46]
Tomato (*Lycopersicon*
esculentum) Decrease in plant nutrient acquisition [47, 48]
Onion (*Allium cepa*) Inhibition of germination process;
reduction of plant biomass
[49]

Cu
Bean (*Phaseolus*
vulgaris) Accumulation of Cu in plant roots;
root malformation and reduction [50]
Black bindweed
(*Polygonum convolvulus*) Plant mortality; reduced biomass and
seed production [51]
Rhodes grass (*Chloris*
gayana) Root growth reduction [52]

Hg
Rice (*Oryza sativa*) Decrease in plant height; reduced tiller
and panicle formation; yield reduction;
bioaccumulation in shoot and root of seedlings
[32, 53]
Tomato (*Lycopersicon*
esculentum) Reduction in germination percentage;
reduced plant height; reduction in flowering
and fruit weight; chlorosis
[54]

Mn
Broad bean (*Vicia faba*) Mn accumulation shoot and root; reduction
in shoot and root length; chlorosis [55]
Spearmint (*Mentha*
spicata) Decrease in chlorophyll a and carotenoid content;
accumulation of Mn in plant roots [56]
Pea (*Pisum sativum*) Reduction in chlorophylls a and b content; reduction
in relative growth rate; reduced photosynthetic O₂
evolution activity and photosystem II activity [57]
Tomato (*Lycopersicon*
esculentum) Slower plant growth; decrease in chlorophyll
concentration
[58]

Ni

Pigeon pea (*Cajanuscajan*) Decrease in chlorophyll content and stomatal conductance; decreased enzyme activity which affected Calvin cycle and CO₂ fixation

[59]

Rye (*Lolium perenne*) grass Reduction in plant nutrient acquisition; decrease in shoot yield; chlorosis

[60]

Wheat (*Triticum* sp.) Reduction in plant nutrient acquisition [61, 62]
Rice (*Oryza sativa*) Inhibition of root growth [63]

Pb

Maize (*Zea mays*) Reduction in germination percentage; suppressed growth; reduced plant biomass; decrease in plant protein content

[64]

Portia (*Thespesia populnea*) tree Reduction in number of leaves and leaf area; reduced plant height; decrease in plant biomass

[65]

Oat (*Avena sativa*) Inhibition of enzyme activity which affected CO₂ fixation

[66]

Zn
Cluster bean (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*) Reduction in germination percentage; reduced plant height and biomass; decrease in chlorophyll, carotenoid, sugar, starch, and amino acid content

[67]

Pea (*Pisum sativum*) Reduction in chlorophyll content; alteration in structure of chloroplast; reduction in photosystem II activity; reduced plant growth

[68]

Rye (*Lolium perenne*) grass Accumulation of Zn in plant leaves; growth reduction; decrease in plant nutrient content; reduced efficiency of photosynthetic energy conversion

[69]

2.3. EFFECT OF HEAVY METAL ON SOIL POLLUTION

Heavy metal pollution in soils constitutes a highly complex disruption of ecological equilibrium. Soils naturally contain a broad diversity of metallic elements, and each metal may be present at variable concentrations and as different chemical species. While some metals have no biological relevance, others are essential trace elements that become toxic when present beyond a certain concentration level. As metals often occur in ionized forms in the soil, they react with negatively charged soil particles, meaning that both their concentrations and their bio availabilities are relevant.

The result of this situation is that soil biota must permanently regulate their activities in order to make essential metals available and take them up in the required concentrations, as well as to exclude or detoxify detrimental forms or concentrations.

In particular, soil microorganisms must display extensive physiological adaptivity. Considering the space and time variability of soils, selection pressure resulting from metal status in soils probably provides an impetus for the adaptation of physiological pathways in soil microorganisms and for their evolution. This is just one example of the complexity of soil, which may explain why the biodiversity of soil microorganisms is so high.

After estimation in 1995, a total amount of over 700 million kg of metals is being dumped in mine tailings worldwide annually (Warhurst, 2002). Depending on the metal (As, Cd, Cu, Ni, Pb, and Zn), the volume of tailing material ranges from 10,000 to 600,000 metric tons (ib.). In India alone about 2000 to 3200 tonnes of elemental Cr escape into the environment annually from the tanning industries, with a Cr concentration ranging between 2000 and 5000 mg L⁻¹ in the effluent

3.4. Sources and Effect of Heavy Metal in Soil: It's Bioremediation

Since the beginning of industrialization, a great variety of anthropogenic chemical compounds have been synthesized for countless uses. The two main sources of heavy metals in soil are natural and anthropogenic/human.

The natural factors include soil erosion, volcanic activities, urban runoffs and aerosols particulate while the human factors include metal finishing and electroplating processes, mining extraction operations, textile industries and nuclear power.

The main natural sources of heavy metal pollutants in the soil are volcanic activities, soil erosion, urban runoffs and aerosol particles. It is reported that volcanic eruptions produce hazardous impacts to the environment, climate, and health of exposed individuals. Apart from the deterioration of social and chemical conditions and the gases (carbon dioxide, sulphur dioxide, carbon monoxide, hydrogen sulphide) released during eruptions, various organic compounds and heavy metals, such as mercury, lead and gold are also released. The presence of these heavy metals in soil and water bodies is known to significantly deteriorate the quality of such soil and waters. Several rocks and volatiles of volcanic origins are indicated to be responsible for the presence of metals in soils and waters. This is because the diffusion of acidic volcanic gases through water permeable rocks contributes to the hydrological material transfer in volcanic strata.

3.5 Sources of Heavy Metals in Contaminated Soils

Due to the disturbance and acceleration of nature's slowly occurring geochemical cycle of metals by man, most soils of rural and urban environments may accumulate one or more of the heavy metals values high enough to cause risks to human health, plants, animals, ecosystems, or other media. The heavy metals essentially become contaminants in the soil environments because:

(i) Their rates of generation via man-made cycles are more rapid relative to natural ones, (ii) they become transferred from mines to random environmental locations where higher potentials of direct exposure occur,

(iii) The concentrations of the metals in discarded products are relatively high compared to those in the receiving environment, and

(iv) The chemical form (species) in which a metal is found in the receiving environmental system may render it more bioavailable.

A simple mass balance of the heavy metals in the soil can be expressed as follows $M_{total} = M_p + M_a + M_f + M_{ag} + M_{ow} + M_{ip} - M_{cr} + M_l$, (1) where "M" is the heavy metal, "p" is the parent material, "a" is the atmospheric deposition, "f" is the fertilizer sources, "ag" are the agrochemical sources, "ow" are the organic waste sources, "ip" are other inorganic pollutants, "cr" is crop removal, and "l" is the losses by leaching, volatilization, and so forth. It is projected that the anthropogenic emission into the atmosphere, for several heavy metals, is one-to-three orders of magnitude higher than natural fluxes. Heavy metals in the soil from anthropogenic sources tend to be more mobile, hence bioavailable than pedogenic, or lithogenic ones.

3.6. Sources and Effect of Heavy Metal in human: It's Bioremediation

Metal-bearing solids at contaminated sites can originate from a wide variety of anthropogenic sources in the form of metal mine tailings, disposal of high metal wastes in improperly protected landfills, leaded gasoline and lead-based paints, land application of fertilizer, animal manures, biosolids (sewage sludge), compost, pesticides, coal combustion residues, petrochemicals, and atmospheric deposition.

a. Fertilizers

Historically, agriculture was the first major human influence on the soil. To grow and complete the lifecycle, plants must acquire not only macronutrients (N, P, K, S, Ca, and Mg), but also essential micronutrients. Some soils are deficient in the heavy metals (such as Co, Cu, Fe, Mn, Mo, Ni, and Zn) that are essential for healthy plant growth, and crops may be supplied with these as an addition to the soil or as a foliar spray. Cereal crops grown on Cu-deficient soils are occasionally treated with Cu as an addition to the soil, and Mn may

similarly be supplied to cereal and root crops. Large quantities of fertilizers are regularly added to soils in intensive farming systems to provide adequate N, P, and K for crop growth. The compounds used to supply these elements contain trace amounts of heavy metals (e.g., Cd and Pb) as impurities, which, after continued fertilizer, application may significantly increase their content in the soil. Metals, such as Cd and Pb, have no known physiological activity. Application of certain phosphatic fertilizers inadvertently adds Cd and other potentially toxic elements to the soil, including F, Hg, and Pb.

b. Pesticides

Several common pesticides used fairly extensively in agriculture and horticulture in the past contained substantial concentrations of metals. For instance in the recent past, about 10% of the chemicals have approved for use as insecticides and fungicides in UK were based on compounds which contain Cu, Hg, Mn, Pb, or Zn. Examples of such pesticides are copper-containing fungicidal sprays such as Bordeaux mixture (copper sulphate) and copper oxychloride. Lead arsenate was used in fruit orchards for many years to control some parasitic insects. Arsenic-containing compounds were also used extensively to control cattle ticks and to control pests in banana in New Zealand and Australia, timbers have been preserved with formulations of Cu, Cr, and As (CCA)., and there are many derelict where soil concentrations of these elements greatly exceed concentrations. Such contamination has the potential to cause problems, particularly if redeveloped for other agricultural or nonagricultural purposes. Compared with fertilizers, the use of such materials has been more localized, being restricted to particular sites or crops.

c. Biosolids and Manures

The application of numerous biosolids (e.g., livestock manures, composts, and municipal sewage sludge) to land inadvertently leads to the accumulation of heavy metals such as As, Cd, Cr, Cu, Pb, Hg, Ni, Se, Mo, Zn, Tl, Sb, and so forth, in the soil. Certain animal wastes such as poultry, cattle, and pig manures produced in agriculture are commonly applied to crops and pastures either as solids or slurries. Although most manures are seen as valuable fertilizers, in the pig and poultry industry, the Cu and Zn added to diets as growth promoters and as contained in poultry health products may also have the potential to cause metal contamination of the soil. The manures produced from animals on such diets contain high concentrations of As, Cu, and Zn and, if repeatedly applied to restricted areas of land, can cause considerable buildup of these metals in the soil in the long run.

Biosolids (sewage sludge) are primarily organic solid products, produced by wastewater treatment processes that can be beneficially recycled. Land application of biosolids materials is a common practice in many countries that allow the reuse of biosolids produced by urban populations. The term sewage sludge is used in many references because of its wide recognition and its regulatory definition. However, the term biosolids is becoming more common as a replacement for sewage sludge because it is thought to reflect more accurately the beneficial characteristics inherent to sewage sludge. It is estimated that in the United States, more than half of approximately 5.6 million dry tonnes of sewage sludge used or

disposed of annually is land applied, and agricultural utilization of biosolids occurs in every region of the country. In the European community, over 30% of the sewage sludge is used as fertilizer in agriculture. In Australia over 175 000 tonnes of dry biosolids are produced each year by the major metropolitan authorities, and currently most biosolids applied to agricultural land are used in arable cropping situations where they can be incorporated into the soil.

There is also considerable interest in the potential for composting biosolids with other organic materials such as sawdust, straw, or garden waste. If this trend continues, there will be implications for metal contamination of soils. The potential of biosolids for contaminating soils with heavy metals has caused great concern about their application in agricultural practices. Heavy metals most commonly found in biosolids are Pb, Ni, Cd, Cr, Cu, and Zn, and the metal concentrations are governed by the nature and the intensity of the industrial activity, as well as the type of process employed during the biosolids treatment. Under certain conditions, metals added to soils in applications of biosolids can be leached downwards through the soil profile and can have the potential to contaminate groundwater. Recent studies on some New Zealand soils treated with biosolids have shown increased concentrations of Cd, Ni, and Zn in drainage leachates.

d. Wastewater

The application of municipal and industrial wastewater and related effluents to land dates back 400 years and now is a common practice in many parts of the world. Worldwide, it is estimated that 20 million hectares of arable land are irrigated with waste water. In several Asian and African cities, studies suggest that agriculture based on wastewater irrigation accounts for 50 percent of the vegetable supply to urban areas. Farmers generally are not bothered about environmental benefits or hazards and are primarily interested in maximizing their yields and profits. Although the metal concentrations in wastewater effluents are usually relatively low, long-term irrigation of land with such can eventually result in heavy metal accumulation in the soil.

e. Metal Mining and Milling Processes and Industrial Wastes

Mining and milling of metal ores coupled with industries have bequeathed many countries, the legacy of wide distribution of metal contaminants in soil. During mining, tailings (heavier and larger particles settled at the bottom of the flotation cell during mining) are directly discharged into natural depressions, including onsite wetlands resulting in elevated concentrations. Extensive Pb and zinc Zn ore mining and smelting have resulted in contamination of soil that poses risk to human and ecological health. Many reclamation methods used for these sites are lengthy and expensive and may not restore soil productivity. Soil heavy metal environmental risk to humans is related to bioavailability. Assimilation pathways include the ingestion of plant material grown in (food chain), or the direct ingestion (oral bioavailability) of, contaminated soil.

Other materials are generated by a variety of industries such as textile, tanning, petrochemicals from accidental oil spills or utilization of petroleum-based products, pesticides, and pharmaceutical facilities and are highly variable in composition. Although some are disposed of on land, few have benefits to agriculture or forestry. In addition, many are potentially hazardous because of their contents of heavy metals (Cr, Pb, and Zn) or toxic organic compounds and are seldom, if ever, applied to land. Others are very low in plant nutrients or have no soil conditioning properties.

f. Air-Borne Sources

Airborne sources of metals include stack or duct emissions of air, gas, or vapor streams, and fugitive emissions such as dust from storage areas or waste piles. Metals from airborne sources are generally released as particulates contained in the gas stream. Some metals such as As, Cd, and Pb can also volatilize during high-temperature processing. These metals will convert to oxides and condense as fine particulates unless a reducing atmosphere is maintained. Stack emissions can be distributed over a wide area by natural air currents until dry and/or wet precipitation mechanisms remove them from the gas stream. Fugitive emissions are often distributed over a much smaller area because emissions are made near the ground. In general, contaminant concentrations are lower in fugitive emissions compared to stack emissions. The type and concentration of metals emitted from both types of sources will depend on site-specific conditions. All solid particles in smoke from fires and in other emissions from factory chimneys are eventually deposited on land or sea; most forms of fossil fuels contain some heavy metals and this is, therefore, a form of contamination which has been continuing on a large scale since the industrial revolution began. For example, very high concentration of Cd, Pb, and Zn has been found in plants and soils adjacent to smelting works. Another major source of soil contamination is the aerial emission of Pb from the combustion of petrol containing tetraethyl lead; this contributes substantially to the content of Pb in soils in urban areas and in those adjacent to major roads. Zn and Cd may also be added to soils adjacent to roads, the sources being tyres, and lubricant oils.

2.4 Basic Soil Chemistry and Potential Risks of Heavy Metals

The most common heavy metals found at contaminated sites, in order of abundance are Pb, Cr, As, Zn, Cd, Cu, and Hg. Those metals are important since they are capable of decreasing crop production due to the risk of bioaccumulation and biomagnification in the food chain. There's also the risk of superficial and groundwater contamination. Knowledge of the basic chemistry, environmental, and associated health effects of these heavy metals is necessary in understanding their speciation, bioavailability, and remedial options. The fate and transport of a heavy metal in soil depends significantly on the chemical form and speciation of the metal. Once in the soil, heavy metals are adsorbed by initial fast reactions (minutes, hours), followed by slow adsorption reactions (days, years) and are, therefore, redistributed into different chemical forms with varying bioavailability, mobility, and toxicity. This distribution is controlled by reactions of heavy metals in soils such as (i) mineral precipitation and dissolution, (ii) ion exchange, adsorption, and desorption, (iii) aqueous complexation, (iv) biological immobilization and mobilization, and (v) plant uptake.

3.4.1. Lead

Lead is a metal belonging to group IV and period 6 of the periodic table with atomic number 82, atomic mass 207.2, density 11.4 g cm^{-3} , melting point 327.4°C , and boiling point 1725°C . It is a naturally occurring, bluish-gray metal usually found as a mineral combined with other elements, such as sulphur (i.e., PbS , PbSO_4), or oxygen (PbCO_3), and ranges from 10 to 30 mg kg^{-1} in the earth's crust. Typical mean Pb concentration for surface soils worldwide averages 32 mg kg^{-1} and ranges from 10 to 67 mg kg^{-1} . Lead ranks fifth behind Fe, Cu, Al, and Zn in industrial production of metals. About half of the Pb used in the U.S. goes for the manufacture of Pb storage batteries. Other uses include solders, bearings, cable covers, ammunition, plumbing, pigments, and caulking. Metals commonly alloyed with Pb are antimony (in storage batteries), calcium (Ca) and tin (Sn) (in maintenance-free storage batteries), silver (Ag) (for solder and anodes), strontium (Sr) and Sn (as anodes in electrowinning processes), tellurium (Te) (pipe and sheet in chemical installations and nuclear shielding), Sn (solders), and antimony (Sb), and Sn (sleeve bearings, printing, and high-detail castings).

Ionic lead, Pb(II), lead oxides and hydroxides, and lead-metal oxyanion complexes are the general forms of Pb that are released into the soil, groundwater, and surface waters. The most stable forms of lead are Pb(II) and lead-hydroxy complexes. Lead(II) is the most common and reactive form of Pb, forming mononuclear and polynuclear oxides and hydroxides. The predominant insoluble Pb compounds are lead phosphates, lead carbonates (form when the pH is above 6), and lead (hydr)oxides. Lead sulfide (PbS) is the most stable solid form within the soil matrix and forms under reducing conditions, when increased concentrations of sulfide are present. Under anaerobic conditions a volatile organolead (tetramethyl lead) can be formed due to microbial alkylation.

Lead (II) compounds are predominantly ionic (e.g., $\text{Pb}^{2+} \text{SO}_4^{2-}$), whereas Pb(IV) compounds tend to be covalent (e.g., tetraethyl lead, $\text{Pb}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4$). Some Pb (IV) compounds, such as PbO_2 , are strong oxidants. Lead forms several basic salts, such as $\text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 2\text{PbCO}_3$, which was once the most widely used white paint pigment and the source of considerable chronic lead poisoning to children who ate peeling white paint. Many compounds of Pb(II) and a few Pb(IV) compounds are useful. The two most common of these are lead dioxide and lead sulphate, which are participants in the reversible reaction that occurs during the charge and discharge of lead storage battery.

In addition to the inorganic compounds of lead, there are a number of organolead compounds such as tetraethyl lead. The toxicities and environmental effects of organolead compounds are particularly noteworthy because of the former widespread use and distribution of tetraethyllead as a gasoline additive. Although more than 1000 organolead compounds have been synthesized, those of commercial and toxicological importance are largely limited to the alkyl (methyl and ethyl) lead compounds and their salts (e.g., dimethyldiethyllead, trimethyllead chloride, and diethyllead dichloride).

Inhalation and ingestion are the two routes of exposure, and the effects from both are the same. Pb accumulates in the body organs (i.e., brain), which may lead to poisoning (plumbism) or even death. The gastrointestinal tract, kidneys, and central nervous system are also affected by the presence of lead. Children exposed to lead are at risk for impaired development, lower IQ, shortened attention span, hyperactivity, and mental deterioration, with children under the age of six being at a more substantial risk. Adults usually experience decreased reaction time, loss of memory, nausea, insomnia, anorexia, and weakness of the joints when exposed to lead. Lead is not an essential element. It is well known to be toxic and its effects have been more extensively reviewed than the effects of other trace metals. Lead can cause serious injury to the brain, nervous system, red blood cells, and kidneys. Exposure to lead can result in a wide range of biological effects depending on the level and duration of exposure. Various effects occur over a broad range of doses, with the developing young and infants being more sensitive than adults. Lead poisoning, which is so severe as to cause evident illness, is now very rare. Lead performs no known essential function in the human body, it can merely do harm after uptake from food, air, or water. Lead is a particularly dangerous chemical, as it can accumulate in individual organisms, but also in entire food chains.

The most serious source of exposure to soil lead is through direct ingestion (eating) of contaminated soil or dust. In general, plants do not absorb or accumulate lead. However, in soils testing high in lead, it is possible for some lead to be taken up. Studies have shown that lead does not readily accumulate in the fruiting parts of vegetable and fruit crops (e.g., corn, beans, squash, tomatoes, strawberries, and apples). Higher concentrations are more likely to be found in leafy vegetables (e.g., lettuce) and on the surface of root crops (e.g., carrots). Since plants do not take up large quantities of soil lead, the lead levels in soil considered safe for plants will be much higher than soil lead levels where eating of soil is a concern (pica). Generally, it has been considered safe to use garden produce grown in soils with total lead levels less than 300 ppm. The risk of lead poisoning through the food chain increases as the soil lead level rises above this concentration. Even at soil levels above 300 ppm, most of the risk is from lead contaminated soil or dust deposits on the plants rather than from uptake of lead by the plant.

3.4.2. Chromium

Chromium is a first-row *d*-block transition metal of group VIB in the periodic table with the following properties: atomic number 24, atomic mass 52, density 7.19 g cm⁻³, melting point 1875°C, and boiling point 2665°C. It is one of the less common elements and does not occur naturally in elemental form, but only in compounds. Chromium is mined as a primary ore product in the form of the mineral chromite, FeCr₂O₄. Major sources of Cr-contamination include releases from electroplating processes and the disposal of Cr containing wastes. Chromium (VI) is the form of Cr commonly found at contaminated sites. Chromium can also occur in the +III oxidation state, depending on pH and redox conditions. Chromium (VI) is the dominant form of Cr in shallow aquifers where aerobic conditions exist. Chromium (VI) can be reduced to Cr (III) by soil organic matter, S²⁻ and Fe²⁺ ions under anaerobic conditions often encountered in deeper groundwater. Major Cr (VI) species include chromate

(CrO_4^{2-}) and dichromate ($\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$) which precipitate readily in the presence of metal cations (especially Ba^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , and Ag^+). Chromate and dichromate also adsorb on soil surfaces, especially iron and aluminum oxides. Chromium (III) is the dominant form of Cr at low pH (<4). Cr^{3+} forms solution complexes with NH_3 , OH^- , Cl^- , F^- , CN^- , SO_4^{2-} , and soluble organic ligands. Chromium (VI) is the more toxic form of chromium and is also more mobile. Chromium(III) mobility is decreased by adsorption to clays and oxide minerals below pH 5 and low solubility above pH 5 due to the formation of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3(\text{s})$. Chromium mobility depends on sorption characteristics of the soil, including clay content, iron oxide content, and the amount of organic matter present. Chromium can be transported by surface runoff to surface waters in its soluble or precipitated form. Soluble and un-adsorbed chromium complexes can leach from soil into groundwater. The leachability of Cr (VI) increases as soil pH increases. Most of Cr released into natural waters is particle associated, however, and is ultimately deposited into the sediment. Chromium is associated with allergic dermatitis in humans.

3.4.3. Arsenic

Arsenic is a metalloid in group VA and period 4 of the periodic table that occurs in a wide variety of minerals, mainly as As_2O_3 , and can be recovered from processing of ores containing mostly Cu, Pb, Zn, Ag and Au. It is also present in ashes from coal combustion. Arsenic has the following properties: atomic number 33, atomic mass 75, density 5.72 g cm^{-3} , melting point 817°C , and boiling point 613°C , and exhibits fairly complex chemistry and can be present in several oxidation states (-III, 0, III, V). In aerobic environments, As (V) is dominant, usually in the form of arsenate (AsO_4^{3-}) in various protonation states: H_3AsO_4 , H_2AsO_4^- , HAsO_4^{2-} , and AsO_4^{3-} . Arsenate and other anionic forms of arsenic behave as chelates and can precipitate when metal cations are present. Metal arsenate complexes are stable only under certain conditions. Arsenic (V) can also coprecipitate with or adsorb onto iron oxyhydroxides under acidic and moderately reducing conditions. Coprecipitates are immobile under these conditions, but arsenic mobility increases as pH increases. Under reducing conditions As(III) dominates, existing as arsenite (AsO_3^{3-}), and its protonated forms H_3AsO_3 , H_2AsO_3^- , and HAsO_3^{2-} . Arsenite can adsorb or coprecipitate with metal sulfides and has a high affinity for other sulfur compounds. Elemental arsenic and arsine, AsH_3 , may be present under extreme reducing conditions. Biotransformation (via methylation) of arsenic creates methylated derivatives of arsine, such as dimethyl arsine $\text{HAs}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ and trimethylarsine $\text{As}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ which are highly volatile. Since arsenic is often present in anionic form, it does not form complexes with simple anions such as Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} . Arsenic speciation also includes organometallic forms such as methylarsinic acid $(\text{CH}_3)\text{AsO}_2\text{H}_2$ and dimethylarsinic acid $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{AsO}_2\text{H}$. Many As compounds adsorb strongly to soils and are therefore transported only over short distances in groundwater and surface water. Arsenic is associated with skin damage, increased risk of cancer, and problems with circulatory system.

3.4.4. Zinc

Zinc is a transition metal with the following characteristics: period 4, group IIB, atomic number 30, atomic mass 65.4, density 7.14 g cm⁻³, melting point 419.5°C, and boiling point 906°C. Zinc occurs naturally in soil (about 70 mg kg⁻¹ in crustal rocks), but Zn concentrations are rising unnaturally, due to anthropogenic additions. Most Zn is added during industrial activities, such as mining, coal, and waste combustion and steel processing. Many foodstuffs contain certain concentrations of Zn. Drinking water also contains certain amounts of Zn, which may be higher when it is stored in metal tanks. Industrial sources or toxic waste sites may cause the concentrations of Zn in drinking water to reach levels that can cause health problems. Zinc is a trace element that is essential for human health. Zinc shortages can cause birth defects. The world's Zn production is still on the rise which means that more and more Zn ends up in the environment. Water is polluted with Zn, due to the presence of large quantities present in the wastewater of industrial plants. A consequence is that Zn-polluted sludge is continually being deposited by rivers on their banks. Zinc may also increase the acidity of waters. Some fish can accumulate Zn in their bodies, when they live in Zn-contaminated waterways. When Zn enters the bodies of these fish, it is able to biomagnify up the food chain. Water-soluble zinc that is located in soils can contaminate groundwater. Plants often have a Zn uptake that their systems cannot handle, due to the accumulation of Zn in soils. Finally, Zn can interrupt the activity in soils, as it negatively influences the activity of microorganisms and earthworms, thus retarding the breakdown of organic matter.

3.4.5. Cadmium

Cadmium is located at the end of the second row of transition elements with atomic number 48, atomic weight 112.4, density 8.65 g cm⁻³, melting point 320.9°C, and boiling point 765°C. Together with Hg and Pb, Cd is one of the big three heavy metal poisons and is not known for any essential biological function. In its compounds, Cd occurs as the divalent Cd(II) ion. Cadmium is directly below Zn in the periodic table and has a chemical similarity to that of Zn, an essential micronutrient for plants and animals. This may account in part for Cd's toxicity; because Zn being an essential trace element, its substitution by Cd may cause the malfunctioning of metabolic processes.

The most significant use of Cd is in Ni/Cd batteries, as rechargeable or secondary power sources exhibiting high output, long life, low maintenance, and high tolerance to physical and electrical stress. Cadmium coatings provide good corrosion resistance coating to vessels and other vehicles, particularly in high-stress environments such as marine and aerospace. Other uses of cadmium are as pigments, stabilizers for polyvinyl chloride (PVC), in alloys and electronic compounds. Cadmium is also present as an impurity in several products, including phosphate fertilizers, detergents and refined petroleum products. In addition, acid rain and the resulting acidification of soils and surface waters have increased the geochemical mobility of Cd, and as a result its surface-water concentrations tend to increase as lake water pH decreases. Cadmium is produced as an inevitable byproduct of Zn and occasionally lead refining. The application of agricultural inputs such as fertilizers, pesticides, and biosolids (sewage sludge), the disposal of industrial wastes or the deposition of atmospheric contaminants increases the total concentration of Cd in soils, and the bioavailability of this Cd determines whether plant Cd uptake occurs to a significant degree. Cadmium is very

biopersistent but has few toxicological properties and, once absorbed by an organism, remains resident for many years.

Since the 1970s, there has been sustained interest in possible exposure of humans to Cd through their food chain, for example, through the consumption of certain species of shellfish or vegetables. Concern regarding this latter route (agricultural crops) led to research on the possible consequences of applying sewage sludge (Cd-rich biosolids) to soils used for crops meant for human consumption, or of using cadmium-enriched phosphate fertilizer.

Cadmium in the body is known to affect several enzymes. It is believed that the renal damage that results in proteinuria is the result of Cd adversely affecting enzymes responsible for reabsorption of proteins in kidney tubules. Cadmium also reduces the activity of delta-aminolevulinic acid synthetase, arylsulfatase, alcohol dehydrogenase, and lipoamide dehydrogenase, whereas it enhances the activity of delta-aminolevulinic acid dehydratase, pyruvate dehydrogenase, and pyruvate decarboxylase. The most spectacular and publicized occurrence of cadmium poisoning resulted from dietary intake of cadmium by people in the Jintsu River Valley, near Fuchu, Japan. The victims were afflicted by itaiitaidisease, which means ouch, ouch in Japanese. The symptoms are the result of painful osteomalacia (bone disease) combined with kidney malfunction. Cadmium poisoning in the Jintsu River Valley was attributed to irrigated rice contaminated from an upstream mine producing Pb, Zn, and Cd. The major threat to human health is chronic accumulation in the kidneys leading to kidney dysfunction. Food intake and tobacco smoking are the main routes by which Cd enters the body.

3.4.6. Copper

Copper is a transition metal which belongs to period 4 and group IB of the periodic table with atomic number 29, atomic weight 63.5, density 8.96 g cm⁻³, melting point 1083°C and boiling point 2595°C. The metal's average density and concentrations in crustal rocks are 8.1 × 10³ kg m⁻³ and 55 mg kg⁻¹, respectively.

Copper is the third most used metal in the world. Copper is an essential micronutrient required in the growth of both plants and animals. In humans, it helps in the production of blood haemoglobin. In plants, Cu is especially important in seed production, disease resistance, and regulation of water. Copper is indeed essential, but in high doses it can cause anaemia, liver and kidney damage, and stomach and intestinal irritation. Copper normally occurs in drinking water from Cu pipes, as well as from additives designed to control algal growth. While Cu's interaction with the environment is complex, research shows that most Cu introduced into the environment is, or rapidly becomes, stable and results in a form which does not pose a risk to the environment. In fact, unlike some man-made materials, Cu is not magnified in the body or bioaccumulated in the food chain. In the soil, Cu strongly complexes to the organic implying that only a small fraction of copper will be found in solution as ionic copper, Cu(II). The solubility of Cu is drastically increased at pH 5.5, which is rather close to the ideal farmland pH of 6.0–6.5.

Copper and Zn are two important essential elements for plants, microorganisms, animals, and humans. The connection between soil and water contamination and metal uptake by plants is determined by many chemical and physical soil factors as well as the physiological properties of the crops. Soils contaminated with trace metals may pose both direct and indirect threats: direct, through negative effects of metals on crop growth and yield, and indirect, by entering the human food chain with a potentially negative impact on human health. Even a reduction of crop yield by a few percent could lead to a significant long-term loss in production and income. Some food importers are now specifying acceptable maximum contents of metals in food, which might limit the possibility for the farmers to export their contaminated crops.

3.4.7. Mercury

Mercury belongs to same group of the periodic table with Zn and Cd. It is the only liquid metal at stp. It has atomic number 80, atomic weight 200.6, density 13.6 g cm⁻³, melting point -13.6°C, and boiling point 357°C and is usually recovered as a byproduct of ore processing. Release of Hg from coal combustion is a major source of Hg contamination. Releases from manometers at pressure-measuring stations along gas/oil pipelines also contribute to Hg contamination. After release to the environment, Hg usually exists in mercuric (Hg²⁺), mercurous (Hg₂²⁺), elemental (Hg₀), or alkylated form (methyl/ethyl mercury). The redox potential and pH of the system determine the stable forms of Hg that will be present. Mercurous and mercuric mercury are more stable under oxidizing conditions. When mildly reducing conditions exist, organic or inorganic Hg may be reduced to elemental Hg, which may then be converted to alkylated forms by biotic or abiotic processes. Mercury is most toxic in its alkylated forms which are soluble in water and volatile in air. Mercury(II) forms strong complexes with a variety of both inorganic and organic ligands, making it very soluble in oxidized aquatic systems. Sorption to soils, sediments, and humic materials is an important mechanism for the removal of Hg from solution. Sorption is pH dependent and increases as pH increases. Mercury may also be removed from solution by coprecipitation with sulphides. Under anaerobic conditions, both organic and inorganic forms of Hg may be converted to alkylated forms by microbial activity, such as by sulfur-reducing bacteria. Elemental mercury may also be formed under anaerobic conditions by demethylation of methyl mercury, or by reduction of Hg(II). Acidic conditions (pH < 4) also favor the formation of methyl mercury, whereas higher pH values favor precipitation of HgS(s). Mercury is associated with kidney damage.

3.4.8. Nickel

Nickel is a transition element with atomic number 28 and atomic weight 58.69. In low pH regions, the metal exists in the form of the nickelous ion, Ni(II). In neutral to slightly alkaline solutions, it precipitates as nickelous hydroxide, Ni(OH)₂, which is a stable compound. This precipitate readily dissolves in acid solutions forming Ni(III) and in very alkaline conditions; it forms nickelite ion, HNiO₂, that is soluble in water. In very oxidizing and alkaline conditions, nickel exists in form of the stable nickelo-nickelic oxide, Ni₃O₄, that is soluble in acid solutions. Other nickel oxides such as nickelic oxide, Ni₂O₃, and nickel peroxide, NiO₂,

are unstable in alkaline solutions and decompose by giving off oxygen. In acidic regions, however, these solids dissolve producing Ni^{2+} .

Nickel is an element that occurs in the environment only at very low levels and is essential in small doses, but it can be dangerous when the maximum tolerable amounts are exceeded. This can cause various kinds of cancer on different sites within the bodies of animals, mainly of those that live near refineries. The most common application of Ni is an ingredient of steel and other metal products. The major sources of nickel contamination in the soil are metal plating industries, combustion of fossil fuels, and nickel mining and electroplating. It is released into the air by power plants and trash incinerators and settles to the ground after undergoing precipitation reactions. It usually takes a long time for nickel to be removed from air. Nickel can also end up in surface water when it is a part of wastewater streams. The larger part of all Ni compounds that are released to the environment will adsorb to sediment or soil particles and become immobile as a result. In acidic soils, however, Ni becomes more mobile and often leaches down to the adjacent groundwater. Microorganisms can also suffer from growth decline due to the presence of Ni, but they usually develop resistance to Ni after a while. Nickel is not known to accumulate in plants or animals and as a result Ni has not been found to biomagnify up the food chain. For animals Ni is an essential foodstuff in small amounts. The primary source of mercury is the sulphide ore cinnabar.

Factors affecting microbial bioremediation

Bioremediation is involved in degrading, removing, altering, immobilizing, or detoxifying various chemicals and physical wastes from the environment through the action of bacteria, fungi and plants. Microorganisms are involved through their enzymatic pathways act as biocatalysts and facilitate the progress of biochemical reactions that degrade the desired pollutant. Microorganisms are act against the pollutants only when they have access to a variety of materials compounds to help them generate energy and nutrients to build more cells. The efficiency of bioremediation depends on many factors; including, the chemical nature and concentration of pollutants, the physicochemical characteristics of the environment, and their availability to microorganisms [4]. The reason for rate of degradation is affected due to bacteria and pollutants do not contact each other. In addition to this, microbes and pollutants are not uniformly spread in the environment. The controlling and optimizing of bioremediation processes is a complex system due to many factors. These factors are included here: the existence of a microbial population capable of degrading the pollutants, the availability of contaminants to the microbial population and environment factors (type of soil, temperature, pH, the presence of oxygen or other electron acceptors, and nutrients).

Biological factors

A biotic factors are affect the degradation of organic compounds through competition between microorganisms for limited carbon sources, antagonistic interactions between microorganisms or the predation of microorganisms by protozoa and bacteriophages. The rate of contaminant degradation is often dependent on the concentration of the contaminant and the amount of “catalyst” present. In this context, the amount of “catalyst” represents the number of organisms able to metabolize the contaminant as well as the amount of enzymes(s)

produced by each cell. The expression of specific enzymes by the cells can increase or decrease the rate of contaminant degradation. Furthermore, the extent to contaminant metabolism specific enzymes must be participated and their “affinity” for the contaminant and also the availability of the contaminant is largely needed. The major biological factors are included here: mutation, horizontal gene transfer, enzyme activity, interaction (competition, succession, and predation), its own growth until critical biomass is reached, population size and composition.

Environmental factors

The metabolic characteristics of the microorganisms and physicochemical properties of the targeted contaminants determine possible interaction during the process. The actual successful interaction between the two; however, depends on the environmental conditions of the site of the interaction. Microorganism growth and activity are affected by pH, temperature, moisture, soil structure, solubility in water, nutrients, site characteristics, redox potential and oxygen content, lack of trained human resources in this field and Physico-chemical bioavailability of pollutants (contaminant concentration, type, solubility, chemical structure and toxicity). This above listed factors are determine kinetics of degradation [5,7]. Biodegradation can occur under a wide-range of pH; however, a pH of 6.5 to 8.5 is generally optimal for biodegradation in most aquatic and terrestrial systems. Moisture influences the rate of contaminant metabolism because it influences the kind and amount of soluble materials that are available as well as the osmotic pressure and pH of terrestrial and aquatic systems [8]. Most environmental factors are listed below.

Availability of nutrients

The addition of nutrients adjusts the essential nutrient balance for microbial growth and reproduction as well as having impact on the biodegradation rate and effectiveness. Nutrient balancing especially the supply of essential nutrients such as N and P can improve the biodegradation efficiency by optimizing the bacterial C: N: P ratio. To survive and continue their microbial activities microorganisms need a number of nutrients such as carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorous. In small concentrations the extent of hydrocarbon degradation also limit. The addition of an appropriate quantity of nutrients is a favourable strategy for increasing the metabolic activity of microorganisms and thus the biodegradation rate in cold environments. Biodegradation in aquatic environment is limited by the availability of nutrients. Similar to the nutritional needs of other organisms, oil-eating microbes also require nutrients for optimal growth and development. These nutrients are available in the natural environment but occur in low quantities.

Temperature

Among the physical factors temperature is the most important one to determining the survival of microorganisms and composition of the hydrocarbons. In cold environments such as the Arctic, oil degradation via natural processes is very slow and puts the microbes under more pressure to clean up the spilled petroleum. The sub-zero temperature of water in this region causes the transport channels within the microbial cells to shut down or may even freeze the entire cytoplasm, thus, rendering most oleophilic microbes metabolically inactive. Biological enzymes are participated in the degradation pathway have an optimum temperature and will not have the same metabolic turnover for every temperature. Moreover, the degradation process for specific compound need specific temperature. Temperature also speed up or slow

down bioremediation process because highly influence microbial physiological properties. The rate of microbial activities increases with temperature, and reaches to its maximum level at an optimum temperature. It became decline suddenly with further increase or decrease in temperature and eventually stop after reaching a specific temperature.

Concentration of oxygen

Different organisms require oxygen others also do not require oxygen based on their requirement facilitate the biodegradation rate in a better way. Biological degradation is carried out in aerobic and anaerobic condition, because oxygen is a gaseous requirement for most living organisms. The presence of oxygen in most cases can enhance hydrocarbon metabolism [12].

Moisture content

Microorganisms require adequate water to accomplish their growth. The soil moisture content have adverse effect in biodegradation agents.

pH

pH of compound which is acidity, basicity and alkalinity nature of compound, it has its own impact on microbial metabolic activity and also increase and decrease removal process. The measurement of pH in soil could indicate the potential for microbial growth. Higher or lower pH values showed inferior results; metabolic processes are highly susceptible to even slight changes in pH.

Metal ions

Metals are important in small amount for bacteria and fungus, but in high quantity inhibit the metabolic activity of the cells. Metal compounds have direct and indirect impact on rate of degradation.

Toxic compounds

When in high concentrations of toxic nature of some contaminants, can create toxic effects to microorganisms and slow down decontamination. The degree and mechanisms of toxicity vary with specific toxicants, their concentration, and the exposed microorganisms. Some organic and inorganic compounds are toxic to targeted life forms

Principle of bioremediation

Bioremediation is defined as the process whereby organic wastes are biologically degraded under controlled conditions to an innocuous state, or to levels below concentration limits established by regulatory authorities. Microorganisms are suited to the task of contaminant destruction because they possess enzymes that allow them to use environmental contaminants as a food. The aim of bioremediation is encouraging them to work by supplying optimum levels of nutrients and other chemicals essential for their metabolism in order to degrade/detoxify substances which is hazardous to environment and living things. All metabolic reactions are mediated by enzymes. These belong to the groups of oxidoreductases, hydrolases, lyases, transferases, isomerases and ligases. Many enzymes have a remarkably

wide degradation capacity due to their non-specific and specific substrate affinity. For bioremediation to be effective, microorganisms must enzymatically attack the pollutants and convert them to harmless products. As bioremediation can be effective only where environmental conditions permit microbial growth and activity, its application often involves the manipulation of environmental parameters to allow microbial growth and degradation to proceed at a faster rate

Bioremediation is occurred naturally and encouraged with in addition of living things and fertilizers. Bioremediation technology is principally based on biodegradation. It refer to complete removal of organic toxic pollutants in to harmless or naturally occurring compounds like carbon dioxide, water, inorganic compounds which are safe for human, animal, plant and aquatic life. Numerous mechanisms and pathways have been elucidated for the biodegradation of a wide variety of organic compounds; for instance, it is completed in the presence and absence oxygen.

4.0. MECHANISMS OF MICROBIAL REMEDIATION OF HEAVY METAL-CONTAMINATED SOILS

The overall objective of any soil remediation approach is to create a final solution that is protective of human health and the environment. Remediation is generally subject to an array of regulatory requirements and can also be based on human health and ecological risks where no legislated standards exist or where standards are advisory. The regulatory authorities will normally accept remediation strategies that centre on reducing metal bioavailability only if reduced bioavailability is equated with reduced risk, and if the bioavailability reductions are demonstrated to be long term. For heavy metal-contaminated soils, the physical and chemical form of the heavy metal contaminant in soil strongly influences the selection of the appropriate remediation treatment approach. The contamination in the soil should be characterized to establish the type, amount, and distribution of heavy metals in the soil. Once the site has been characterized, the desired level of each metal in soil must be determined. This is done by comparison of observed heavy metal concentrations with soil quality standards for a particular regulatory domain, or by performance of a site-specific risk assessment. Remediation goals for heavy metals may be set as total metal concentration or as leachable metal in soil, or as some combination of these.

To survive under metal stressed condition, bacteria have evolved several types of mechanisms.

These mechanisms of removal of heavy metals include the efflux of metal ions outside the cell, accumulation and forms complex of the metal ions inside the cell and later reduce the toxic metal ions to a non-toxic state. The microorganisms involved in this process may belong to bacteria, fungi, yeast and algae. Potent metal biosorbents under the class of bacteria include the genera of *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Streptomyces* and *P. aeruginosa*. Amongst the various microorganisms, fungal biomasses were very effective due to presence of high percentage of cell wall material, which may have the excellent metal binding capacity. Many fungi and yeast have excellent biosorption potential includes the genera of *Rhizopus*, *Aspergillus*, *Streptoverticillum* and *Sacchromyces*.

High levels of heavy metals are harmful to biota in environment including microorganisms. For endurance under metal-stressed environment, plant growth promoting Rhizobacteria have evolved several mechanisms by which they can immobilize, mobilize or transform metals rendering them inactive to tolerate the uptake of heavy metal ions.

Several technologies exist for the remediation of metal-contaminated soil. Gupta et al. have classified remediation technologies of contaminated soils into three categories of hazard-alleviating measures:

- (i) Gentle in situ remediation,
- (ii) In situ harsh soil restrictive measures, and
- (iii) In situ or ex situ harsh soil destructive measures.

The goal of the last two harsh alleviating measures is to avert hazards either to man, plant, or animal while the main goal of gentle in situ remediation is to restore the malfunctionality of soil (soil fertility), which allows a safe use of the soil. At present, a variety of approaches have been suggested for remediating contaminated soils. Has broadly classified remediation technologies for contaminated soils into

- (i) Source control and
- (ii) Containment remedies.

Source control involves **in situ and ex situ** treatment technologies for sources of contamination. In situ means that the contaminated soil is treated in its original place; unmoved, unexcavated; remaining at the site or in the subsurface.

- **In situ treatment technologies** treat or remove the contaminant from soil without excavation or removal of the soil.
- **Ex situ** means that the contaminated soil is moved, excavated, or removed from the site or subsurface. Implementation of ex situ remedies requires excavation or removal of the contaminated soil. Containment remedies involve the construction of vertical engineered barriers (VEB), caps, and liners used to prevent the migration of contaminants.

Another classification places remediation technologies for heavy metal-contaminated soils under five categories of general approaches to remediation isolation, immobilization, toxicity reduction, physical separation, and extraction. The key factors that may influence the applicability and selection of any of the available remediation technologies are:

- I. Cost,
- II. Long-Term Effectiveness/Permanence,
- III. Commercial Availability,

- IV. General Acceptance.
- V. Applicability to High Metal Concentrations.
- VI. Applicability to Mixed Wastes (Heavy Metals and Organics).
- VII. Toxicity Reduction.
- VIII. Mobility Reduction, And
- IX. Volume Reduction.

4.1. Solidification/Stabilization (S/S)

Solidification involves the addition of binding agents to a contaminated material to impart physical/dimensional stability to contain contaminants in a solid product and reduce access by external agents through a combination of chemical reaction, encapsulation, and reduced permeability/surface area. Stabilization (also referred to as fixation) involves the addition of reagents to the contaminated soil to produce more chemically stable constituents. Conventional S/S is an established remediation technology for contaminated soils and treatment technology for hazardous wastes in many countries in the world.

The general approach for solidification/stabilization treatment processes involves mixing or injecting treatment agents to the contaminated soils. Inorganic binders such as clay (bentonite and kaolinite), cement, fly ash, blast furnace slag, calcium carbonate, Fe/Mn oxides, charcoal, zeolite, and organic stabilizers such as bitumen, composts, and manures, or a combination of organic-inorganic may be used. The dominant mechanism by which metals are immobilized is by precipitation of hydroxides within the solid matrix. Solidification/stabilization technologies are not useful for some forms of metal contamination, such as species that exist as oxyanions (e.g., $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$, AsO_3^-) or metals that do not have low-solubility hydroxides (e.g., Hg). Solidification/stabilization may not be applicable at sites containing wastes that include organic forms of contamination, especially if volatile organics are present. Mixing and heating associated with binder hydration may release organic vapors. Pretreatment, such as air stripping or incineration, may be used to remove the organics and prepare the waste for metal stabilization/solidification. The application of S/S technologies will also be affected by the chemical composition of the contaminated matrix, the amount of water present, and the ambient temperature.

4.2. Soil Washing

Soil washing is essentially a volume reduction/waste minimization treatment process. It is done on the excavated (physically removed) soil (ex situ) or on-site (in situ). Soil washing refers to ex situ techniques that employ physical and/or chemical procedures to extract metal contaminants from soils. During soil washing, (i) those soil particles which host the majority of the contamination are separated from the bulk soil fractions (physical separation), (ii) contaminants are removed from the soil by aqueous chemicals and recovered from solution on a solid substrate (chemical extraction), or (iii) a combination of both. In all cases, the separated contaminants then go to hazardous waste landfill (or treated by chemical, thermal, or biological processes). By removing the majority of the contamination from the soil, the bulk fraction that remains can be (i) recycled on the site being remediated as relatively inert backfill, (ii) used on another site as fill, or (iii) disposed of relatively cheaply as nonhazardous material.

Ex situ soil washing is particularly frequently used in soil remediation because it

- (i) Completely removes the contaminants and hence ensures the rapid cleanup of a contaminated site,
- (ii) Meets specific criteria,
- (iii) Reduces or eliminates long-term liability,
- (iv) May be the most cost-effective solution,
- (v) May produce recyclable material or energy.

The disadvantages include the fact that the contaminants are simply moved to a different place, where they must be monitored, the risk of spreading contaminated soil and dust particles during removal and transport of contaminated soil, and the relatively high cost. Excavation can be the most expensive option when large amounts of soil must be removed, or disposal as hazardous or toxic waste is required.

Acid and chelator soil washing are the two most prevalent removal methods. Soil washing currently involves soil flushing an in situ process in which the washing solution is forced through the in-place soil matrix, ex situ extraction of heavy metals from the soil slurry in reactors, and soil heap leaching. Another heavy metal removal technology is electroremediation, which mostly involves electrokinetic movement of charged particles suspended in the soil solution, initiated by an electric gradient. The metals can be removed by precipitation at the electrodes. Removal of the majority of the contaminants from the soil does not mean that the contaminant-depleted bulk is totally contaminant free. Thus, for soil washing to be successful, the level of contamination in the treated bulk must be below a site-specific action limit (e.g., based on risk assessment). Cost effectiveness with soil washing is achieved by offsetting processing costs against the ability to significantly reduce the amount of material requiring costly disposal at a hazardous waste landfill.

Typically the cleaned fractions from the soil washing process should be >70–80% of the original mass of the soil, but, where the contaminants have a very high associated disposal

cost, and/or where transport distances to the nearest hazardous waste landfill are substantial, a 50% reduction might still be cost effective. There is also a generally held opinion that soil washing based on physical separation processes is only cost effective for sandy and granular soils where the clay and silt content (particles less than 0.063 mm) is less than 30–35% of the soil. Soil washing by chemical dissolution of the contaminants is not constrained by the proportion of clay as this fraction can also be leached by the chemical agent.

However, clay-rich soils pose other problems such as difficulties with materials handling and solid-liquid separation. Full-scale soil washing plants exist as fixed centralized treatment centres, or as mobile/transportable units. With fixed centralized facilities, contaminated soil is brought to the plant, whereas with mobile/transportable facilities, the plant is transported to a contaminated site, and soil is processed on the site. Where mobile/transportable plant is used, the cost of mobilization and demobilization can be significant. However, where large volumes of soil are to be treated, this cost can be more than offset by reusing clean material on the site (therefore avoiding the cost of transport to an off-site centralized treatment facility, and avoiding the cost of importing clean fill).

4.3. Principles of Soil Washing

Soil washing is a volume reduction/waste minimization treatment technology based on physical and/or chemical processes. With physical soil washing, differences between particle grain size, settling velocity, specific gravity, surface chemical behaviour, and rarely magnetic properties are used to separate those particles which host the majority of the contamination from the bulk which are contaminant-depleted.

The equipment used is standard mineral processing equipment, which is more generally used in the mining industry.

Chemical soil washing, soil particles are cleaned by selectively transferring the contaminants on the soil into solution. Since heavy metals are sparingly soluble and occur predominantly in a sorbed state, washing the soils with water alone would be expected to remove too low an amount of cations in the leachates, chemical agents have to be added to the washing water. This is achieved by mixing the soil with aqueous solutions of acids, alkalis, complexants, other solvents, and surfactants.

The resulting cleaned particles are then separated from the resulting aqueous solution. This solution is then treated to remove the contaminants (e.g., by sorption on activated carbon or ion exchange).

The effectiveness of washing is closely related to the ability of the extracting solution to dissolve the metal contaminants in soils. However, the strong bonds between the soil and metals make the cleaning process difficult. Therefore, only extractants capable of dissolving large quantities of metals would be suitable for cleaning purposes. The realization that the goal of soil remediation is to remove the metal and preserve the natural soil properties limits the choice of extractants that can be used in the cleaning process.

4.4 Chemical Extractants for Soil Washing

Owing to the different nature of heavy metals, extracting solutions that can optimally remove them must be carefully sought during soil washing. Several classes of chemicals used for soil washing include surfactants, cosolvents, cyclodextrins, chelating agents, and organic acids. All these soil washing extractants have been developed on a case-by-case basis depending on the contaminant type at a particular site. A few studies have indicated that the solubilization/exchange/extraction of heavy metals by washing solutions differs considerably for different soil types. Strong acids attack and degrade the soil crystalline structure at extended contact times. For less damaging washes, organic acids and chelating agents are often used as alternatives to straight mineral acid use.

Natural, low-molecular-weight organic acids (LMWOAs) including oxalic, citric, formic, acetic, malic, succinic, malonic, maleic, lactic, aconitic, and fumaric acids are natural products of root exudates, microbial secretions, and plant and animal residue decomposition in soils. Thus metal dissolution by organic acids is likely to be more representative of a mobile metal fraction that is available to biota. The chelating organic acids are able to dislodge the exchangeable, carbonate, and reducible fractions of heavy metals by washing procedures. Although many chelating compounds including citric acid, tartaric acid, and EDTA for mobilizing heavy metals have been evaluated, there remain uncertainties as to the optimal choice for full-scale application.

The identification and quantification of coexisting solid metal species in the soil before and after treatment are essential to design and assess the efficiency of soil-washing technology. A study that changes in Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd, and Pb speciation and uptake by maize in a sandy loam before and after washing with three chelating organic acids indicated that EDTA and citric acid appeared to offer greater potentials as chelating agents for remediating the permeable soil. Tartaric acid was used for moderate contamination.

The use of soil washing to remediate contaminated fine-grained soils that contained more than 30% fines fraction has been reported by several workers. Khodadoust et al. have also studied the removal of various metals (Pb, Ni, and Zn) from field and clay (kaolin) soil samples using a broad spectrum of extractants (chelating agents and organic acids). Chen and Hong reported on the chelating extraction of Pb and Cu from an authentic contaminated soil using derivatives of iminodiacetic acid and L-cysteine. Wuana et al. studied the removal of Pb and Cu from kaolin and bulk clay soils using two mineral acids (HCl and H₂SO₄) and chelating agents (EDTA and oxalic acid). The use of chelating organic acids—citric acid, tartaric acid and EDTA in the simultaneous removal of Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd, and Pb from an experimentally contaminated sandy loam was carried out by Wuana et al.. These studies furnished valuable information on the distribution of heavy metals in the soils and their removal using various extracting solutions.

4.5. Phytoremediation

Phytoremediation, also called green remediation, botanoremediation, agroremediation, or vegetative remediation, can be defined as an in situ remediation strategy that uses vegetation and associated microbiota, soil amendments, and agronomic techniques to remove, contain, or render environmental contaminants harmless. The idea of using metal-accumulating plants to remove heavy metals and other compounds was first introduced in 1983. Plants may break down or degrade organic pollutants or remove and stabilize metal contaminants. The methods used to phytoremediate metal contaminants are slightly different from those used to remediate sites polluted with organic contaminants. Phytoremediation is energy efficient, aesthetically pleasing method of remediating sites with low-to-moderate levels of contamination, and it can be used in conjunction with other more traditional remedial methods as a finishing step to the remedial process.

The **advantages** of phytoremediation compared with classical remediation are that

- (i). it is more economically viable using the same tools and supplies as agriculture,
- (ii). it is less disruptive to the environment and does not involve waiting for new plant communities to recolonize the site,
- (iii). disposal sites are not needed,
- (iv). it is more likely to be accepted by the public as it is more aesthetically pleasing than traditional methods,
- (v). it avoids excavation and transport of polluted media thus reducing the risk of spreading the contamination, and
- (vi). it has the potential to treat sites polluted with more than one type of pollutant.

The **disadvantages** are as follow

- (i). it is dependant on the growing conditions required by the plant (i.e., climate, geology, altitude, and temperature),
- (ii). large-scale operations require access to agricultural equipment and knowledge,
- (iii). success is dependant on the tolerance of the plant to the pollutant,
- (iv). contaminants collected in senescing tissues may be released back into the environment in autumn,
- (v). contaminants may be collected in woody tissues used as fuel,
- (vi). time taken to remediate sites far exceeds that of other technologies,

(vii). contaminant solubility may be increased leading to greater environmental damage and the possibility of leaching.

Potentially useful phytoremediation technologies for remediation of heavy metal-contaminated soils include phytoextraction (phytoaccumulation), phytostabilization, and phytofiltration.

4.6. Phytoextraction (Phytoaccumulation)

Phytoextraction is the name given to the process where plant roots uptake metal contaminants from the soil and translocate them to their above soil tissues. A plant used for phytoremediation needs to be heavy-metal tolerant, grow rapidly with a high biomass yield per hectare, have high metal-accumulating ability in the foliar parts, have a profuse root system, and a high bioaccumulation factor.

Phytoextraction is a (green) remediation technology. There are two forms of phytoextraction of heavy metals, namely, 1. **Continuous or Natural Phytoextraction and**

2. Chemically Enhanced Phytoextraction.

Continuous or Natural Phytoextraction
Continuous phytoextraction is based on the use of natural hyperaccumulator plants with exceptional metal-accumulating capacity. Hyperaccumulators are species capable of accumulating metals at levels 100-fold greater than those typically measured in shoots of the common nonaccumulator plants. Thus, a hyperaccumulator plant will concentrate more than 10 mg kg⁻¹ Hg, 100 mg kg⁻¹ Cd, 1000 mg kg⁻¹ Co, Cr, Cu, and Pb; 10 000 mg kg⁻¹ Zn and Ni. Hyperaccumulator plant species are used on metalliferous sites due to their tolerance of relatively high levels of pollution. Approximately 400 plant species from at least 45 plant families have been so far, reported to hyperaccumulate metals; some of the families are Brassicaceae, Fabaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Asterraceae, Lamiaceae, and Scrophulariaceae . Crops like alpine pennycress (*Thlaspicaerulescens*), Ipomea alpine, *Haumaniastrum robertii*, *Astragalus racemosus*, *Sebertia acuminata* have very high bioaccumulation potential for Cd/Zn, Cu, Co, Se, and Ni, respectively. Willow (*Salix viminalis* L.), Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea* L.), corn (*Zea mays* L.), and sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) have reportedly shown high uptake and tolerance to heavy metals.

A number of processes are involved during phytoextraction of metals from soil:

- (I). A metal fraction is sorbed at root surface,
- (ii). Bioavailable metal moves across cellular membrane into root cells,
- (iii). A fraction of the metal absorbed into roots is immobilized in the vacuole,
- (iv). Intracellular mobile metal crosses cellular membranes into root vascular tissue (xylem), and

(v).Metal is translocated from the root to aerial tissues (stems and leaves).

Once inside the plant, most metals are too insoluble to move freely in the vascular system so they usually form carbonate, sulphate, or phosphate precipitate immobilizing them in apoplastic (extracellular) and symplastic (intracellular) compartments. Hyperaccumulators have several beneficial characteristics but may tend to be slow growing and produce low biomass, and years or decades are needed to clean up contaminated sites. To overcome these shortfalls, chemically enhanced phytoextraction has been developed. The use of high biomass crops that are induced to take up large amounts of metals when their mobility in soil is enhanced by chemical treatment with chelating organic acids.

Conclusion

Plants growing on heavy metal polluted soils show a reduction in growth due to changes in their physiological and biochemical activities. This is especially true when the heavy metal involved does not play any beneficial role towards the growth and development of plants. Bioremediation can be effectively used for the treatment of heavy metal polluted soil. It is most appropriate when the remediated site is used for crop production because it is a non-disruptive method of soil remediation. Using plants for bioremediation (phytoremediation) is a more common approach to bioremediation of heavy metal compared with the use of microorganisms. Plants employ different mechanisms in the remediation of heavy metal polluted soils. Phytoextraction is the most common method of phytoremediation used for treatment of heavy metal polluted soils. It ensures the complete removal of the pollutant. Combining both plants and microorganisms in bioremediation increases the efficiency of this method of remediation. Both mycorrhizal fungi and other PGPR have been successfully incorporated in various phytoremediation programs. The success of the combined use of these organisms depends on the species of microbe and plants involved and to some extent on the concentration of the heavy metal in soil.

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